

An automated CI/CD process for testing and deployment of Network Applications over 5G infrastructure

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Abstract—As 5G standards have largely matured, further enabling the radical development of 5G networks, the pressure for mobile operators to keep up with widening range of industry and contemporary use cases increases. Consequently, many approaches are emerged from the perspective of the vertical’s interaction with the 5G system especially while onboarding specific vertical Network Applications (or NetApps). This work discusses an approach which reduces the complexity of this interaction by introducing a novel yet standard based vertical onboarding model. Our approach focuses on preserving interoperability and reproducibility with other systems through the exclusive utilization of data models derived by embracing well-known industry standards. Being also pragmatic, the mechanisms presented in this paper are implemented and applied in a large distributed 5G infrastructure.

Keywords—5G, automated deployment and testing, unified input data model, standardized data models

I. INTRODUCTION

The so called 5G system aims to provide higher capacity and lower latency while increasing the level of programmability, control and flexibility in order to meet the requirements stemming from innovative use-cases from various vertical factors. To reduce the time-to-market for novel 5G Network Applications (NetApps) from third party developers, embracing a Development and Operations (DevOps) methodology is an agile and modern way to move forward. Novel procedures and novel fully automated toolchains are needed, that cater the production of any NetApp with very little or without human interaction through Operations Support Systems (OSS) automation tools of the 5G system.

The work presented in this paper, which is in the context of a large 5G research project called “*Fifth generation (5G) Application & Services experimentation and certification Platform (5GASP)*” aims at accelerating small and mid-size enterprises (SMEs) towards the “new world” of 5G-based Network Applications (NetApps) which shall empower various verticals with unique capabilities that will unleash the potential in respect to the “real-world” use of 5G technologies. 5GASP strives to achieve a long-term goal: the development of a self-sustainable community of 5G researchers, developers and vertical end-users that can disseminate knowledge about i) how to develop NetApps, ii) how to test them under close-to-real conditions; and iii) how to certify their NetApps, before they finally reach their targeted Network Operators and/or Vertical industry customers. These novelties are demonstrated on top of well-known and mature 5G facilities,

5G services and 5G/Network Function Virtualization (NFV) experimentation tools to overall offer a DevOps-like, open platform for deploying, validating, verifying and certifying NetApps.

5GASP builds and operates an Open, and Inter-Domain 5G NFV-based Reference (Open5G-NFV) ecosystem of distributed experimental facilities. This ecosystem integrates mature 5G facilities across Europe and lays down the foundations for instantiating fully softwarised architectures of vertical industries. Furthermore, it provides processes, resources, and a toolchain to test and validate NetApps taking into consideration vertical-specific requirements.

This paper is organized as follows: we first overview the work from other notable related research (Section II). Next section presents the overall 5GASP facility (Section III). Following this, a novel, automated Continuous integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline is introduced (Section IV) alongside with our proposed fully standards-compliant unified data model that triggers this process (Section V). Then, the description of deployment and orchestration (Section VI), along with the testing phase (Section VII) completes the automation circle. Lastly, a presentation of our prototype implementation (Section VIII) follows, as we end up with the conclusion and our foresight on how our work will further advance the NFV (Section IX).

II. RELATED WORK

Several EU 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5GPPP) projects [1] have devoted great efforts to design and develop distributed end to end 5G platforms with the aim of providing automated validation of network applications and services to 5G developers and experimenters. In the following, we focus on 5GPPP research projects which are recently finished or still on-going, whereas emphasizing on the aforementioned scope.

The 5GinFIRE project [2] (H2020 ICT-13-2016) aimed to automate the previously described testing phase. To do so, it introduced the concept of DevOps. Jenkins [3], a CI/CD server, was introduced in the testing stage and a testing pipeline was configured. This pipeline was triggered every time a package was submitted to the 5GinFIRE Portal. After the testing pipeline was completed, the Portal was informed about the results obtained. To make this possible, Jenkins Remote Access API was used for the Portal to communicate with Jenkins.

5GTango [4] was a project funded by H2020 program, under the ICT-2016-2 call, lasting from 2017 to 2020. It provided a vendor-agnostic Management and Orchestration (MANO) platform, that besides offering all functionality of the MANO framework, also offered a Service Development Kit (SKD) for the verification and validation of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). This SKD was responsible for validating the syntax, integrity, and topology of the submitted VNFs. After these validations, the VNFs were functionally tested, by deploying the Network Service on an emulated scenario and checking if the VNFs worked as expected. 5GTango's testing phase required many and complex configurations. Besides, the involvement of a human was necessary during the testing process, to create the test plans.

5GEVE [5] is an on-going project funded by the H2020 program under the ICT-17-2018 call. Its objective is to offer a 5G End-to-End (E2E) facility to 5G experimenters to enable the experimentation and validation with full set of 5G capabilities. 5GEVE proposes an automated model-based testing, which is supported by the use of a set of templates and blueprints. The workflow starts with a test requirement gathering performed by the 5GEVE infrastructure operators. With this information, they can define the experiment blueprints for the designed 5G service or application, adapted to a certain site, which may include custom scripts provided by the developer. Once the experiment is defined, its execution is scheduled, and the results are provided to the developers.

5G-VINNI [6] (on-going, H2020 ICT-17-2017) aims to develop an E2E facility that validates the performance of 5G technologies performing trials of advanced vertical sector services. To achieve this, the facility offers a practical implementation of the infrastructure to support the key 5G Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), to then allow verticals to test and validate specific applications that are dependent upon these KPIs. They use the concept of Test as a Service (TaaS) to simplify testing operations, providing an interface to connect the CI/CD pipelines and offering an integrated set of tools that enable and facilitate the testing cycles [7].

VITAL-5G [8] is a H2020 project (ICT-41-2020) that started simultaneously with 5GASP. Its objective is to improve the transport and logistics (T&L) services by engaging SMEs and logistics stakeholders, offering them an open, secure, and virtualized 5G environment to test, validate and verify their NetApps. For that purpose, the project aims to create an open service validation platform to offer third parties, such as SMEs, a place where validate their T&L solutions and services using real-life resources and facilities,

as they will be deployed in production systems. For that purpose, they aim to perform extensive technical and business validations, focusing on NetApps flexibility and scalability, and on the performance of the vertical applications.

The innovation of 5GASP project is mainly focused on the operations and secured/trusted service provisioning, leveraging multiple experimental facilities that feature virtualized and software implemented functions. The testbed addresses the needs of a SME community that can foster the adoption, the innovation and the benefits of 5G technologies. 5GASP will support them to achieve this objective with technology and knowledge provided by project partners, as well as an open call to other experts and newcomers.

III. THE 5GASP FACILITY

The overall 5GASP facility is composed of several interworking 5G testbeds, each deployed at a different geographic location and defining a single administrative domain. Every 5GASP facility site includes the following components:

- A NFV Orchestrator (NFVO), taking care of the lifecycle management of provided network services that comprise the host network slice, the deployed NetApp and any automated tests tailored for this designated scenario.
- A Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM), responsible for controlling and managing the NFV infrastructure computing, storage, and network resources within each site's infrastructure domain.
- Infrastructure resources, including access, transport, and core network functions bundled together to describe the supported use cases.
- A Testcase Execution Engine (TEE), which performs and executes automated tests against the deployed NetApp on the facility.

All the components defined in each site can be from the same or different vendors, and all managed by a single operator. Despite this per-site description, the whole facility is viewed as a single platform from the NetApp developer's perspective. This brings the need to implement adaptation layers, which unify the behavior and features offered in the different sites, abstracting underlying implementation details.

In this context, 5GASP envisions the option to provide developers with a one-stop single entry-point to the facility by means of web services and open APIs, a so called 5GASP portal. This one-stop single entry-point allows a 5G NetApp developer to: i) seamlessly onboard its NetApp on a 5G system, ii) specify the accommodating site to host it, and iii) describe the tests, or select them from a provided repository, that should be triggered once the NetApp is deployed.

IV. CI/CD TESTING AND DEPLOYMENT PROCESS

This section contains a description of the onboarding and deployment process, triggered by the interaction of the developer with the 5GASP portal, as depicted in Figure 1. The 5GASP portal and its APIs are exposed to the developer as a single entry-point to the 5GASP system by integrating various standardised data models from major telecommunications standard bodies (e.g. TM Forum, GSMA, 3GPP). By doing so, the system offers interoperability and reproducibility capabilities aligned with existing industry approaches. Further

Figure 1. CI/CD Deployment and Testing Process

elaboration on the proposed model that is utilized can be found in the next section.

The CI/CD Deployment and Testing Process (Figure 1) is instantiated once the 5GASP portal receives the corresponding NetApp onboarding action from the developer in the form of the proposed NFV model. Our approach envisages a CI/CD Service as the main actor of the entire procedure with a main role to orchestrate the deployment pipeline in coordination with additional services residing both in 5GASP portal and the underlying facilities. To that extend, once developer’s onboarding action triggers the process, the CI/CD Service conducts a set of pre-flight validation checks with the aim of verifying the syntax and semantics of the NetApp descriptor, among other verifications. If the NetApp passes this validation step, the flow is redirected to the 5GASP portal allowing for the process to continue.

At this stage, the portal services are tasked with the deployment of the NetApp. This operation employs a Service Orchestrator integrated in the portal, which initially i) requests a proper network slice from an appointed facility site to act as a host of the NetApp, facilitating its network requirements, and then ii) onboards and deploys the onboarded NetApp on the provided network slice. The successful completion of this step transfers the flow back to the CI/CD Service.

Once the NetApp is deployed, the CI/CD Service is anticipated to execute a set of tests either selected from predefined suites or provided during the initial onboarding process by the developer. For this purpose, the test Execution Engine (TEE) is recruited in the relevant facility site, which performs the supplied automated tests against the NetApp or the infrastructure itself. Predictably, test results are streamed back to the 5GASP portal and should the nominal case of expected behavior and execution be met, the NetApp is labeled as “5GASP certified”, along with a reference to the certification process information. Ultimately, a certified NetApp is published in the 5GASP store, thus rendering it available to the public, accelerating the deployment process for onboarding to 3rd party production 5G systems.

V. PROPOSED NETAPP ONBOARDING MODEL

To provide a unified abstraction for all sites, the necessary experiment modelling and transformations need to be defined so that onboarding, activation and testing can properly performed not only on any 5GASP facility but also to any NFV/3GPP compliant 5G System, regardless of the internal details. To achieve this, we propose a unified standards-based model that has the form of a “**triplet**” of entities triggering a service deployment order, as depicted in Figure 2. This “**triplet**” consists of the following entities:

- The onboarded NetApp to be activated within the deployed 5G slice.
- The Network Slice that needs to be activated by the target 5G facility, with specific requirements.
- The test suite, described in terms of a test descriptors model, that will be executed after the activation of the NetApp.

The main aim of the “**triplet**” approach is to define each part of the unified model towards the same resource model, that provides a complete description of a given service, including information on topology and expected behavior. To that extend, 5GASP’s approach for each entity of the

Figure 2. 5GASP NetApp onboarding model

“**triplet**”, i.e. NetApps, hosting network slices, and test suite descriptors, is to be defined under the TMF’s ServiceSpecification model [9]. ServiceSpecification is a class that offers characteristics to describe a type of service. Functionally, it acts as a template by which Network Services may be instantiated.

A. Onboarded NetApp model

To support our TMF model adoption approach, onboarded NetApps will be referred as ResourceFacing ServiceSpecifications, expressing the resource aspects of the NetApps with their respective requirements. These NetApps will be described as Virtual Network Function Descriptors (VNFDs) or Network Service Descriptors (NSDs), depending on the defined model (YANG [10] or TOSCA [11]). As enhancements of the NFV architecture towards “Cloud-native” are currently attempted, 5GASP aims to provide effortless transformation for already containerized applications to NSDs/VNFs via Kubernetes Helm Charts, leveraging deployment schemes described in [12]. Prior to a successful onboarding, a set of elementary pre-flight tests, i.e. syntax, semantics, and reference checking, will be conducted to certify the validity of the descriptor to be onboarded. Should this step be successful, then the hosting network slice requirements shall be introduced.

B. The Network Slice model

The hosting network slice requirements need to be defined in a standardized way. While onboarding the NetApp we can distinguish between two options for the Network Slice specification to be achieved: i) the developer may select the accommodating site to onboard its NetApp through a list of explicitly reported network slice specifications, or ii) 5GASP system will automatically appoint each NetApp to a target site, based on more abstract network requirements input from the developer. Whichever the appointed case may be, network requirements will be fully aligned with GSMA’s GST [13] properties and each designated site will provide information on the range of network requirements it supports in form of NESTs. Therefore, these templates will be either available to the developer to choose from or there will be automatically allocated, depending on the NetApp fulfilling its requirements. Each one of the populated properties in NESTs will be perceived as a ServiceSpecCharacteristic resource

class, representing a key feature of the service specification by describing the hosting network slice.

C. The Test suite descriptors model

At early stages, testing may be carried out through pre-defined automated test cases already described in each facility site and offered during the onboarding process. Initially, these tests will be focused on the validation of specific infrastructure related KPIs. Later on the project, the test cases will be divided in three different categories, according to their objective and their scope: (i) Infrastructure tests, (ii) Custom test scripts, and (iii) Custom VNF-based tests. The infrastructure tests will be performed either at the moment when the NetApp is deployed, or whenever the rest of the tests are triggered. These tests will evaluate infrastructure related metrics, such as deployment time, latency, or availability. Both the custom test scripts and the custom VNF-based tests will be defined by the experimenters in order to evaluate certain characteristics or behavior of the NetApps. These kinds of tests will be stored in a test repository and they will be offered to NetApp developers and experimenters during the onboarding procedure. Thus, the goal of this idea is to have a significative collection of tests in the repository to ease the testing and validation design of NetApps for unexperienced developers. The reference to each test case can also be achieved via the adoption of ServiceSpecification model.

D. The “triplet” entities as a unified model

These three experimental model entities, converted to ServiceSpecification resource models, can be contained, and listed in service catalogue(s). The design and maintenance of a service catalogue brings benefits both in terms of reusability and classification of the “triplet’s” entities to distinct and explicit groups. Furthermore, the introduction of a catalogue aims to incorporate these templates, which are conceived to provide a self-contained specification of offered service instances, so that their deployment and operation can be automated as much as possible.

Once all entities are expressed to the aforementioned unified model, then bundling to a single entity can be achieved and progressed through underlying components for fulfillment. The concept of this unique entity can be served through TMF’s Service Order model [14]. Once a Service Order is placed, the service fulfillment process is instantiated via a Service Orchestrator which supports the delivery process as per the requested specification, gets the full decomposition up to the required network level operations and executes them onto an administrative domain.

VI. NETAPPS DEPLOYMENT AND ORCHESTRATION

The previous section defined the procedure of gathering the 5GASP tenant’s (NetApp Developer) input, the so called “triplet”, forming the Service Deployment Order. Then, as order is captured by the 5GASP system, the fulfilment process is instantiated as illustrated in Figure 3.

Here, order fulfilment and delivery are happening in two layers. By Service Orchestrator and then by NFVO. Although the Service Orchestrator resides within the 5GASP portal, the NFVO is facility site specific, thus the two-layer distinction. Service Orchestration is aware of all underlying facility sites and their respective network capabilities and it is responsible of coordinating the service deployment through certain steps, as depicted in Figure 3, simultaneously ensuring that each step is successfully progressed through. A service order may

Figure 3. Service Order fulfillment and delivery

trigger orchestration process in a single facility site, or it may involve a cross-domain orchestration. In the latter case, Service Orchestrator may collaborate with a Network Orchestrator to establish a multi-site deployment.

As outlined above, to initiate the process, the Service Orchestrator transforms the properties of the provided NEST into network requirements, which are then requested to be accommodated by the underlying facility site(s). Each facility site implements a set of those NESTs and once requested, it deploys the respective service to facilitate the network requirements accordingly, e.g. User Plane Function (UPF) stitching, Core or Edge deployment depending on latency inputs, or placing into the 5G core as an Application Function (3GPP AF). Once the network slice is properly prepared on site’s infrastructure, NetApp deployment request is expected and thus, the flow returns to Service Orchestrator for that matter. Eventually, NetApp is deployed on the previously prepared host network slice. Lastly, tests defined in the provided test descriptor are executed on the recently deployed NetApp/slice and further discussed in the next section.

VII. TESTING PHASE

Once the NetApp is deployed, the testing phase begins. As previously mentioned, each testbed hosts the so-called TEE, that is responsible for selecting and performing the NetApp tests, using the testing descriptor as input provided by the NetApp’s developer “triplet”.

5GASP’s CI service is not only composed of Local TEEs. The testing requests will be submitted to a Master TEE, which will, then, forward the testing jobs to the Local TEEs. In each testbed, a Local Test Repository (LTR) is also deployed. It contains a set of pre-configured tests, specific for that testbed, that will be gathered and executed by the TEE. Besides performing pre-configured tests, the TEE may also perform dynamic tests, that were defined in the testing descriptors provided by the NetApps’ developers. It is expected that the NetApps are validated against i) performance tests, ii) functional tests, and iii) reliability tests.

Throughout the testing of the NetApps, several infrastructure metrics will be collected. Furthermore, the Local TEEs will be responsible for creating a log of all the performed tests and a report that presents the results of the NetApp testing. This report will be sent to the Master TEE, which will then publish them on a dashboard. This dashboard will not only contain the testing reports but also the infrastructure metrics that were collected during the test of the NetApp.

It is expected that the NetApp’s developer receives automatic feedback after the testing phase. To do so, 5GASP’s Portal will notify him, via email, once the testing of the

NetApp has ended, providing a URL to access the dashboard mentioned before.

VIII. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

A. The 5GASP portal solution

The 5GASP portal solution is based on the open-source project Openslice [15]. Openslice employs a service-based architecture and design which utilizes 3GPP and ETSI standards, TM Forum OpenAPIs and delivers Network Slices as Services (NSaaS). Also, it offers a user-friendly UI, multi-tenancy, support for onboarding VNFs to target facility NFVO and an Open API based on TMF family of APIs making it a perfect candidate for facilitating the project’s needs.

Openslice is currently aligned with TMF909’s proposed API Component Suite in support of a set of Operational Domains exposing and managing “Network” Services [16]. This component suite was selected, as not only it covers the functionalities required by Operational Domains to interwork with OSS/BSS applications and/or other domains from service providers or 3rd parties, but it also accommodates one of the key requirements of Openslice, that is the reusability of API functionality rather than using a large set of specific APIs. The employed Operation Domain management functions and capabilities are illustrated in Figure 4. Openslice extends TMF909’s vision for the emerging cases that the 5G domain needs through the introduction of three main lifecycle phases, i.e. slice ordering, fulfillment, and operation. Further elaboration on operational scenario can be found in [17].

Openslice’s key contribution is that allows SMEs or organizations to implement private network scenarios that interact with public large-scale networks in a standardized matter.

B. CI/CD and Test Execution Engine (TEE)

The 5GASP CI/CD service is composed of one Jenkins Master Node and several Jenkins Slave Nodes. Each testbed is composed of, at least, one Jenkin Slave Node, which will act as the TEE. Furthermore, each testbed will also have one LTR. The communication between the Master Node and the slaves will be enabled by Wireguard [18] tunnels. To do so,

we will use a VNF that dynamically creates Wireguard tunnels between independent domains.

After the pre-flight validation stage, the 5GASP Portal will call a Test Configuration Module, that is responsible for i) given the test descriptor, choosing the testbed to deploy the NetApp, ii) dynamically creating a Jenkins Job configuration, and iii) submitting this configuration to the CI/CD Master Node, via the Jenkins REST API. This triggers the CI/CD service.

Once triggered, the Jenkins Master Node will forward the Job execution to the Slave Node that resides on the chosen testbed. The Slave Node will then call the Openslice API to obtain the NetApp and the full testing descriptor.

After the NetApp is deployed, the testing phase begins. The Jenkins Slave Node will then obtain several pre-configured tests from the LTR and validate the NetApp against them. These tests can be defined via Robot Framework [19], given its good integration with Jenkins. As mentioned in section IV, during the testing phase, several log files will be created and combined into a final test report. This report will be sent to a service that will allow the developer to visualize a dashboard with the results of the tests. A URL to access this service will be sent to the 5GASP Portal, so that the developer knows how to access the service. The developer will also be notified when the testing phase is concluded.

IX. CONCLUSION

The presented approach aims to create mechanisms that allow the testing of NetApps under close-to-real conditions. To do so, our approach is implemented on the distributed 5G infrastructure of 5GASP. 5GASP presents a testbed where the developers may deploy and test their NetApps. In this paper, we propose a CI/CD service to automate this process. The CI/CD service will coordinate with the 5GASP Portal, local TEEs, and LTRs to ensure the correct deployment and validation of the NetApps.

5GASP's single testbed offers an abstraction for the multiple independent testbeds being used, each deployed in different regions and with different characteristics. Given the testbeds heterogeneity, flexibility and abstraction are of utmost importance, during the deployment and testing process.

Previously, we presented our view on how to achieve a complete automated deployment and testing of the NetApps in our testbed - from the onboarding of the NetApps, to its testing. Given the novelty of our work, we expect to encounter several challenges and drawbacks. Once surpassed, we will reach a completely automated pipeline for testing NetApps. This will allow a faster certification process, enabling a faster deployment of the NetApps on Network Operators and Vertical Industry customers. We are certain that the contributions of our work will lead to advancements in NFV.

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Figure 4. Operational Domain Management Functions and Capability (source: [16])

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